

Bacterial Contamination of Laboratory Equipment in a Tertiary Care Hospital, Rawalpindi

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Enrollment No: 2020-RMC-0033 | BSc Honours — Medical Laboratory Technology (2021–2025)

ABSTRACT

Introduction:	Equipment frequently used in the laboratory as well as in hospitals harbours potential pathogens and may act as a source of infectious agents. The ability of potential pathogens to persist for longer periods of time on inanimate surfaces and instruments has increased the risk of hospital-acquired infections (HAIs). This study aimed to determine the bacterial contamination of commonly used equipment in the pathology laboratory of a tertiary care hospital, Rawalpindi.
Objective:	To determine the type of microbial contamination on different laboratory equipment used in a tertiary care hospital, Rawalpindi.
Methods:	A total of 100 samples were collected from the less-used and the most-used sites of different equipment. Plain cotton-tipped sterilised swabs moistened with Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) were used for sample collection. Samples were cultured on enriched media for isolation and identification of bacterial pathogens. Colonies were Gram-stained and subjected to biochemical analysis, followed by antibiotic susceptibility testing using standard microbiological techniques.
Results:	Out of 100 samples, 78% bacterial isolates were recovered from equipment; 14% were environmental contaminants (<i>Bacillus</i> species) and 8% showed no growth. <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> was the most common bacterial isolate (50% of 78%). Among <i>S. aureus</i> isolates, 28% were MRSA. <i>Klebsiella</i> species was the most common Gram-negative isolate, followed by <i>E. coli</i> and <i>Pseudomonas</i> species.
Conclusion:	High bacterial contamination of frequently used pathology laboratory equipment with a variety of potential pathogens and environmental contaminants was detected. <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> was the most common bacterial isolate. This study highlights the need for regular disinfection of instruments after use and improved hand hygiene among laboratory personnel.

Keywords: laboratory equipment; bacterial contamination; *Staphylococcus aureus*; MRSA; hospital-acquired infections; disinfection; pathology laboratory.

1. INTRODUCTION

Infection control is highly stressed in today's practice of pathology laboratory. Research has shown that improper disinfection of the pathology environment can transmit infectious diseases and prove to be a health hazard to both laboratory personnel and patients [1]. This can be fatal for immunodeficient patients. Although it

is well-known that the laboratory environment — which includes instruments, laboratory materials, and laboratory units — can serve as a means of cross-contamination, there is limited data on the microbial involvement [2,3].

Transmission of diseases in laboratory settings can occur: (1) from the patient to the laboratory worker, (2) from the laboratory worker to the patient, (3) from one worker to another, and (4) from the laboratory to the community. With the increase in transmissible diseases due to saliva or blood contamination, the laboratory has an important task of minimising these risks by following strict aseptic principles. Routine infection control — including maintenance of hand hygiene, disinfection, and contact isolation — is essential to prevent nosocomial infections [4]. The colonisation of potentially pathogenic microorganisms on various inanimate surfaces present in a laboratory setup, such as incubators, centrifuges, pipettes, patient files, and microscopes, has been reported as a potential vehicle for transmission of nosocomial pathogens from laboratory healthcare personnel [5].

Indoor environments are important since most individuals spend a large proportion of their lives indoors. Bacterial communities in these environments are of particular interest; in-depth studies of environmental bacteria over the last decade have shed light on their subtle effects on human health. For instance, chronic exposure to bacteria can cause asthma, whereas early-life exposure to various moulds and their derivatives may protect children from allergic and autoimmune diseases [6]. A growing body of literature has helped estimate bacterial diversity in various indoor environments and revealed that bacterial diversity is closely related to weather conditions, population density, and internal ventilation conditions [7].

Microbial contamination is one of the biggest worldwide obstacles for researchers working with microbial cultures. False-positive cultures are reported from microbial laboratories due to common and unusual laboratory contaminants. High microbial contamination occurs in microbial laboratories due to lack of proper management. It is a global concern regarding health and leads to difficulty in obtaining accurate research output. In order to reduce contamination, good laboratory practice and appropriate procedural instructions must first be applied [1,8].

Cross-contamination in the laboratory is a growing concern, with several studies finding that transmission of infection occurs mainly through contaminated or improperly disinfected laboratory equipment, or through improper handling of clinical items after arrival at the laboratory. Certain bacteria that are not part of normal flora can cause serious infections if passed to laboratory personnel or patients. Infection control programmes should be developed and implemented before handling any laboratory items [9].

Bacterial contamination of the laboratory is considered a major risk factor for hospital-acquired infections (HAIs). Infection control and basic hygiene should be the first priority of good hospital management [11]. Approximately 10% of all infections can have serious consequences in terms of increased healthcare professional morbidity, mortality, and length of laboratory stay, particularly with multi-drug resistant strains such as methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). Antimicrobial resistance results in increased illness, deaths, and healthcare costs [10,11].

The knowledge of microorganisms harbouring laboratory equipment and laboratory attire is important for minimising cross-contamination and improving the safety of both laboratory workers and laboratory technicians [14]. Identification of microorganisms from commonly used laboratory instruments and laboratory attire will help in the implementation of required sterilisation and disinfection methods, thereby improving patient safety by reducing the risk of nosocomial infections.

The aim of the current study was to identify the critical sources of bacterial contamination inside the laboratory and to describe appropriate and necessary options to prevent microbial cross-contamination, reduce false-positive culture reports, and maximise the accuracy of results from the microbiological laboratory [16].

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Bacterial contamination of hospital equipment, including laboratory equipment, is one of the most probable causes of nosocomial infections. These infections are acquired by patients while in a hospital or other clinical

care facility and can also affect workers, visitors, delivery personnel, and anyone who has contact with the laboratories. The Centre for Disease Control (CDC) estimates that about 10% of all hospital patients acquire some type of nosocomial infection as a result of contact with contaminated hospital equipment. Of approximately 40 million people admitted to hospitals annually, 2 to 4 million may develop an infection they did not have upon entering [17].

A study in Kano State, Nigeria collected one hundred swabs from hospital equipment that came in contact with patients at five different hospitals. The results showed that 76% of swabs were positive for bacterial growth. Isolated bacteria included *Corynebacterium* spp. (10%), *Lactobacillus* spp. (8%), *Staphylococcus* spp. (52%), and *Streptococcus* spp. (6%). Isolation of potential pathogens on the surface of hospital equipment indicated that these items predispose patients to nosocomial infections, sometimes with lethal repercussions for both patients and healthcare providers [3].

Another study conducted at the Microbiology Department, Kohat University of Science and Technology, Pakistan (March–June 2014) collected five samples from different areas including tables, floors, clothing, air, and incubators. A total of 22 bacterial contaminants were isolated and identified by biochemical tests. *Staphylococcus epidermidis* was the most common contaminant (36.36%), followed by *Bacillus* (31.81%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (18.18%), and Diptheroids (13.63%) [1].

A descriptive cross-sectional study at Kashan University of Health Sciences examined 75 computer keyboards and inanimate electronic devices in five ICUs during 2016–2017. Samples were cultured on Blood Agar and MacConkey Agar and growing bacteria were identified by colony morphology and biochemical properties. Results showed that 76% of equipment were contaminated with bacteria and fungi. Gram-positive bacteria dominated (70.7%), with coagulase-negative staphylococcus being the most isolated species [9].

A study at Ayder Comprehensive Specialty Hospital, Mekelle, Northern Ethiopia collected 130 swab samples (84 from medical instruments; 46 from inanimate surfaces). Bacterial growth was detected in 115 (88.5%) swab samples. Bacterial contaminants were isolated from 70 (83.3%) medical equipment and 45 (97.8%) inanimate surfaces [5,18].

A study at a tertiary care hospital in Pokhara, Nepal collected 232 samples and recovered 219 bacterial isolates from 181 samples. *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most common bacterial strain (44/219). Among the isolates of *S. aureus*, 36.3% (16/44) were methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). Of the 44 isolates, 12 (29.5%) were multidrug resistant and 14 (31.8%) were biofilm producers. The majority of MRSA isolates (62.5%) were biofilm producers. *Acinetobacter* was the most common Gram-negative organism, followed by *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas* species [20].

3. AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To determine the type of microbial contamination on different laboratory equipment used in a tertiary care hospital, Rawalpindi.

4. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

4.1 Study Design

Descriptive cross-sectional study.

4.2 Study Duration

Three months after approval of the Research Proposal.

4.3 Sample Size

A total of 100 samples were included in the study.

4.4 Study Setting

Pathology Laboratory, Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi.

4.5 Inclusion Criteria

Samples were collected from the most-used and less-used sites of laboratory equipment, including laboratory machines and electronics of the tertiary care hospital, Rawalpindi. Only samples from working laboratory instruments without prior intimation to the cleaning staff were included.

4.6 Exclusion Criteria

Freshly disinfected equipment was excluded from the study.

4.7 Sample Collection

Two sterilised swabs were used for each piece of equipment: one for sampling the most-used site and another for the less-used site. Plain, cotton-tipped, sterilised swabs moistened with 1 mL Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) were used. Swabs were passed up and down and rolled on the desired surfaces, then immediately transported to the laboratory. Swabs were incubated for 24 hours and examined the next day for turbidity, then immediately streaked onto Blood Agar and MacConkey's Agar and incubated overnight at 37°C.

4.8 Microbiological Methods

Bacterial colonies on agar plates were Gram-stained and examined under 100× magnification. Bacterial isolates were subjected to the following biochemical tests for identification:

- **Catalase Test:** Used to differentiate catalase-producing bacteria such as staphylococci from non-catalase-producing bacteria such as streptococci.
- **Citrate Test:** Used to identify Enterobacteriaceae based on the ability of an organism to use citrate as its sole carbon source. A positive reaction (bright blue colour) is obtained with *Klebsiella pneumoniae*; *Escherichia coli* gives a negative reaction.
- **Oxidase Test:** Used to assist in identification of *Pseudomonas*, *Neisseria*, *Vibrio*, and *Pasteurella*. A positive reaction produces a deep purple colour in the phenylenediamine reagent.
- **SIM Test (Sulphide, Indole, Motility):** A semisolid agar medium inoculated to test for hydrogen sulphide production, indole production, and motility of the organism. H₂S production is detected when ferrous sulphide (black precipitate) is formed.
- **Triple Sugar Iron (TSI) Test:** Used to assess fermentation of glucose, lactose, and sucrose, and production of hydrogen sulphide. Results are interpreted from the butt and slant of the agar tube based on colour change and gas production.
- **MRSA Identification:** Cefoxitin disc (30 µg) was used for identification of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). A zone size of <21 mm indicates resistance (MRSA); ≥22 mm indicates methicillin-sensitive *S. aureus* (MSSA).

4.9 Data Analysis

All collected data were tabulated and analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 25) software.

5. RESULTS

This study was conducted by taking 50 samples from the most-used sites and 50 samples from the less-used sites of laboratory equipment in a tertiary care hospital. Majority of equipment showed different types of bacterial growth and were contaminated, while a few were free of contamination, as depicted in the following tables and figures.

Table 1. Bacterial growth percentage of equipment samples (n = 100)

Growth Status	Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
Growth	92	92.0	98.0	98.0

No Growth	8	8.0	2.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	—

On the basis of Gram-stained smears, Gram-positive organisms appeared purple while Gram-negative organisms stained pink. *Staphylococcus* appeared in clusters and *Bacillus* in rod form. The following table shows the frequencies of different pathogenic and non-pathogenic bacteria isolated from two different sites of equipment. Non-pathogenic bacteria include *Bacillus* species, whereas the majority of isolated bacteria are pathogens.

Table 2. Frequency distribution of bacterial contaminants isolated from laboratory equipment

Organism Isolated	Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
MRSA	28	28.0	28.0	28.0
Bacillus species	14	14.0	14.0	42.0
Staphylococcus aureus	22	22.0	22.0	64.0
Staphylococcus species	17	17.0	17.0	81.0
Klebsiella species	6	6.0	6.0	87.0
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	4	4.0	4.0	91.0
E. coli	1	1.0	1.0	92.0
No Growth	8	8.0	8.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

The study revealed that out of 100 samples, 78% bacterial isolates were recovered from equipment and 14% were environmental contaminants such as *Bacillus* species, while the remaining 8% showed no growth. *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most common bacterial isolate (50% of 78%). The majority of *S. aureus* isolates were recovered from the most frequently used sites of the equipment. Among the *S. aureus* isolates, 28% were MRSA. *Klebsiella* species was the most common Gram-negative isolate, followed by *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas* species. Frequently used sites showed greater bacterial contamination than less-used sites, highlighting the role of hand contact in pathogen transmission.

6. DISCUSSION

Microbial contamination of equipment in the pathology laboratory as well as in hospitals is generally considered a risk factor for healthcare workers and laboratory personnel. Bacterial contamination of frequently used laboratory instruments contributes to a high risk of hospital-acquired infections (HAIs). Isolation of potential pathogens like MRSA, *Acinetobacter* species, *Pseudomonas*, and *Escherichia coli* poses a threat of transmission among hospital and community populations. Findings of this study are important for emphasising hand hygiene and regular disinfection of equipment. Availability of hand sanitiser and hand washing practices after contact with equipment and objects may reduce the possibility of transmission of potential pathogens [20].

Decontamination of these sites with alcohol-based disinfectants would reduce the microbial flora. The CDC and multiple leaders in the field have suggested that routine cleaning of medical equipment with antimicrobial agents, especially in the vicinity of personnel, is necessary. Maintaining the chain of cleanliness, decreasing microorganism load, and targeted eradication of sources of infection have already been shown to decrease HAIs and eliminate outbreaks. Clinically significant organisms have been shown to persist on equipment for months, making disinfection essential [21].

The bacteriological profile of frequently used equipment yielded a wide variety of organisms, ranging from environmental contaminants to potential pathogens. In this study, out of 100 samples, 76% showed pathogenic growth while 14% were environmental contaminants. *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most common bacterial isolate (50%). A similar study in Kano State, Nigeria (2012) yielded 52% isolates of *S. aureus*, of which 25% were MRSA [3].

Staphylococcus aureus is a well-known nosocomial pathogen with the ability to survive in the hospital environment for several days. Its ability to form biofilm on inanimate objects prolongs survival and spread [22]. The majority of bacterial isolates in this study were MRSA, which is alarming, as this strain embedded in biofilm can survive for extended durations and can become a potential source of MRSA-associated nosocomial and community infections.

Biofilm formation is an important determinant of the survival of *S. aureus* [23]. Coagulase-negative *Staphylococcus* species were isolated from 17% of equipment sites in this study. *Klebsiella* species was the most common Gram-negative isolate, in contrast to a study by Health Research Services (2013), where *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was dominant (30%) [26]. *Pseudomonas* accounted for only 4% in the present study. *E. coli* was present on the autoclave (1%), while a study in Pokhara, Nepal (2013) reported 15% contamination with *E. coli* [27].

The major non-pathogen isolated was *Bacillus* species (14%), as it is an environmental contaminant. Out of the total, 8% samples showed no growth. Frequently used sites showed more bacterial contamination than less-used sites, underscoring the importance of transmission of potential pathogens through improper hand hygiene practices [28].

7. CONCLUSION

- High microbial contamination was observed on equipment. *Staphylococcus* species including MRSA, *Klebsiella*, *Pseudomonas*, and *E. coli* were the major pathogens isolated.
- Laboratory equipment has been shown to harbour potential pathogens and may play a role in the nosocomial transmission of pathogenic micro-organisms.
- Human activity plays a major role in microbial control; meticulous cleaning and strict adherence to standard operating procedures (SOPs) is essential.
- Preventive measures may be achieved by improving cleaning and disinfection of equipment on a daily basis after use.

8. REFERENCES

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